

Distributed Machine Learning: Based on Computational resources available

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Abstract—We propose a novel dynamic distributed training framework that applies distributed learning principles over a local area network (LAN). Each node in the network runs a unified Python-based agent (using Flask and PyTorch) and self-benchmarks its GPU performance using *glmark2*. The node with the lowest benchmark score is elected master, while others become workers. Workers train a shared neural network on distinct partitions of the MNIST dataset and send their local model weights to the master after each epoch. The master performs Softmax function based aggregation of these models and redistributes the updated global model. This approach tailors the training workload to hardware heterogeneity and avoids centralizing data. We discuss the system architecture, implementation details (including Flask API endpoints, multithreading, and error handling), and deployment insights such as node discovery. Our results demonstrate the feasibility of adaptive distributive training in a LAN setting. This work lays groundwork for more resilient and scalable distributed systems that leverage local resources without sharing raw data.

Keywords—*Distributed Machine Learning, Benchmark-Based Node Ranking, Role Assignment, Adaptive Weight Aggregation, Parallel Training, LAN-based Collaboration, Glmark2 Benchmark*

I. INTRODUCTION

Training modern machine learning (ML) models, especially neural networks on a single device is often a time-consuming and resource-intensive process, particularly when the dataset is large or the hardware is not optimized for high-performance computing. In many educational, research, or edge-computing environments, practitioners rely on standard laptops or desktops without dedicated GPUs. When training is performed serially on such a device, it can take hours or even days to reach convergence, depending on the complexity of the model and dataset. This significantly slows down iteration cycles, model experimentation, and deployment timelines.

This issue becomes more severe in collaborative or academic settings, where multiple team members may be working with the same dataset but are constrained by hardware limitations. Despite being physically co-located and connected over a common local area network (LAN), these devices often remain underutilized during training sessions, as the computational burden is placed solely on one node. This represents a lost opportunity to parallelize and distribute the workload in a meaningful, efficient way. To address this challenge, we propose a LAN-based,

role-aware distributive training framework that distributes the training workload across multiple devices based on their computational capability. Instead of relying on cloud servers or centralized GPU clusters, our approach harnesses the collective power of heterogeneous nodes—such as laptops or desktops connected via Wi-Fi in a lab or classroom—to collaboratively train a shared model. The system automatically:

- Discovers nearby nodes within the subnet,
- Benchmarks their compute capability using the *glmark2* performance tool.
- Elects a master node dynamically, and assigns roles and partitions data accordingly.

The key methodological feature of our system is its softmax-weighted aggregation of model parameters. Rather than averaging model updates blindly, our system uses the benchmark score of each worker node to compute softmax-based contribution weights. This allows faster or more reliable nodes to influence the global model more than slower, less consistent participants. Additionally, a custom synchronizer module ensures that the master node waits for all required weight updates before aggregating, thereby enforcing synchronous training rounds and preventing premature or incomplete updates....

This project validates the system using the MNIST image classification dataset[5], leveraging a lightweight multi-layer perceptron (MLP) architecture for experimentation. The framework supports full-round FL simulations on real hardware over Wi-Fi without requiring any cloud backend. Through this work, we demonstrate a scalable and practical design for compute-aware FL in edge-centric environments with heterogeneous devices.

II. RELATED WORK

Javani and Wang (2024)[5] proposed a load balancing strategy grounded in the Age of Information (AoI) concept. The paper introduces a load metric X defined as the number of rounds between subsequent selections of a client. Their goal is to minimize the variance $\text{Var}[X]$ which stabilizes client participation frequency and ensures fair workload distribution. A key contribution is the development of a Markov chain-based decentralized client scheduling policy, where each client makes autonomous decisions based on its local "age" (the number of rounds since its last

participation). This method eliminates the need for centralized coordination and is scalable to large networks. Their simulation results demonstrated that minimizing $\text{Var}[X]$ significantly improves the convergence speed and model accuracy by ensuring consistent update intervals and reducing bias due to under- or over-utilized clients. On datasets like MNIST, CIFAR-10, and CIFAR-100, the proposed method reduced communication rounds needed for convergence by 9% to 20%, compared to random client selection.

The paper "*Delayed Gradient Averaging: Tolerate the Communication Latency for Federated Learning*" [6] addresses the challenge of high communication latency in federated learning by introducing **Delayed Gradient Averaging (DGA)** a method that allows local training to proceed while communication and model synchronization are delayed. By overlapping computation and communication, DGA significantly improves training throughput without compromising convergence or accuracy. The method is theoretically justified and empirically validated using a 16-node Raspberry Pi cluster, showing up to 4× speedups over traditional FedAvg. However, while the paper effectively mitigates communication delays, it assumes homogeneous device capabilities and lacks mechanisms to handle **load imbalance** or **heterogeneous compute power**, a **gap** directly targeted by our compute-aware federated training framework.

Research Gap:

1. The proposed method assumes all clients are equally capable in terms of compute power, memory, and training speed.
2. Their focus is on participation fairness (i.e., minimizing the variance in selection intervals) rather than training efficiency or system throughput.
3. Clients make participation decisions based on how long it has been since they were last selected, not on how fast they can actually train a model or how suitable they are for the current task.

III. KEY CONCEPTS

A. Benchmark-Driven Node Ranking

In traditional federated learning systems, client selection is often random or uniform. However, in real-world scenarios, devices have varying computational capabilities, which can lead to inefficient load distribution and delayed training rounds. To address this, we introduce a benchmark-based ranking mechanism, where each participating node computes a performance score using the `glmark2` benchmarking tool.

Let $\text{rank}_i \in \mathbb{R}$ denote the benchmark score of node i . Higher scores indicate stronger compute power (e.g., presence of a GPU or better CPU). These scores serve two purposes:

Automatic role assignment, where the node with the lowest score is elected as the master node.

Weight determination in the federated aggregation process, as described in Section 3.3.

This technique ensures that nodes contribute proportionally to their compute capacity, improving both fairness and efficiency.

B. Softmax-Based Weight Normalization

To translate the raw benchmark scores into a normalized probability distribution suitable for parameter aggregation, we apply the softmax function. Given a set of ranks $\{\text{rank}_1, \text{rank}_2, \dots, \text{rank}_K\}$ from K participating nodes, the aggregation weight w_i for node i is computed as:

$$w_i = \frac{e^{\frac{\text{rank}_i}{\tau}}}{\sum_{j=1}^K e^{\frac{\text{rank}_j}{\tau}}}$$

Here, τ is a temperature hyperparameter that controls the sensitivity of the exponential function. In our implementation, $\tau=1000$ is chosen empirically to maintain numerical stability across a wide range of benchmark scores.

This formulation ensures all weights are strictly positive and sum to 1, forming a valid convex combination. Nodes with higher benchmark scores (i.e., better performance) receive higher weights during model aggregation.

C. Cross-Entropy Loss for Multi-Class Classification

The objective function optimized during local training is the cross-entropy loss, commonly used in classification tasks. Given a predicted class probability distribution p and a one-hot encoded ground truth label y , the cross-entropy loss is defined as:

$$L(p, y) = \sum_{k=1}^C y_k \log p_k \quad (4)$$

where C is the number of classes.

In our case, this corresponds to the 10-digit classes in the MNIST dataset.

Minimizing this loss encourages the model to assign high probability to the correct class, thereby improving prediction accuracy.

D. Synchronization and Barrier Enforcement

To maintain consistency across training rounds, the master node employs a synchronization barrier that ensures all worker nodes have uploaded their weights before aggregation begins. Formally, aggregation is triggered only when:

$$L(p, y) = \forall i \in \{1, \dots, K\}, \text{received}_i = \text{True} \quad (5)$$

This condition is checked via a Synchronizer class that records receipt flags for each epoch. The barrier mechanism ensures synchronous rounds, prevents stale updates, and improves model stability.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. System Assumptions

All devices reside in the same /24 subnet and can reach each other over TCP port 5000.

Python (≥ 3.8), PyTorch, Flask, and the CPU benchmark `glmark2` are pre-installed.

One shared dataset (e.g., MNIST) is locally accessible to the elected master; workers receive only index lists, never raw samples.

B. Phase 0 - Node Initialisation

Benchmark Execution happens when each node calculates numeric score using `glmark2` and then the score is stored in the rank of each node.

During initialization, the program script launches a Flask server on each node to handle communication between devices in the distributed learning setup. The server exposes several HTTP routes that enable synchronization and model weight exchange across nodes:

`/benchmark` (GET): This route allows other nodes to retrieve the current node's benchmark score and IP address. It is used during the role assignment phase to identify the fastest node.

`/receiveweights` (POST): Worker nodes use this route to upload their locally trained model weights to the master node. The master stores and records these weight files for aggregation.

`/weights` (GET): This route is used to download the latest model weights. Workers use it to retrieve the global model from the master after aggregation, while the master can also request weights from workers if needed.

`/aggregation_status` (GET): Worker nodes poll this endpoint to check whether the master has completed aggregating the weights for the current training round. This ensures synchronization before proceeding to the next epoch.

`/aggregation_complete` (POST): Once the master finishes aggregating the weights, it sends a notification to all workers using this route, signaling that the global model is ready for download.

C. Phase 1 - Peer Discovery & Role Election

Each node scans the local network to discover active peers and fetch their benchmark scores via `/benchmark`. The node with the lowest score is elected as the master, and all others with valid scores become workers.

Algorithm 1:

```

1 active ← ping-sweep(local /24) #Section discover_nodes
2 ranks ← {self_ip: rank_self}
3 for ip ∈ active \ self_ip:
4 r ← GET http://ip:5000/benchmark
5 ranks[ip] ← r.score (-1 on failure)
6 master ← argmin{ ranks[ip] | ranks[ip] ≥ 0 }
7 ROLE ← "master" if self_ip = master else "worker"
8 WORKER_NODES ← {ip | ip ≠ master ∧ ranks[ip] ≥ 0}

```

D. Phase 2 - Dataset Partitioning (master only)

The master loads `datasets.MNIST(PATH)` and slices the index set $\{0, \dots, N-1\}$ into contiguous, equal-sized chunks (Algorithm 2).

Algorithm 2:

```

P ← sorted(WORKER_NODES)
n ← |P|, s ← ⌊N / n⌋
for i, ip in enumerate(P):
    start ← i·s
    end ← (i+1)·s if i < n-1 else N
    chunk[ip] ← [start, ..., end-1]
return chunk

```

Each worker retrieves its index list through the launch-time `all_node_indices_map`.

E. Phase 3 - Local Training on Workers

During each global epoch $e \in \{0, 1, \dots, E-1\}$, every worker node performs the following operations:

Data Preparation:

The worker constructs a `PyTorch DataLoader` using a subset of the MNIST dataset assigned specifically to its IP address. This subset is accessed via:

```
DataLoader(Subset(MNIST, indices[ip]), batch_size=32)
```

Model and Optimizer:

Each node uses the same neural network architecture, a fully connected Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) defined as:

Input (28×28) → Hidden (128) → Output (10 classes)

The model is trained using Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) with a learning rate:

$\eta = 0.01$

Local Training:

For each mini-batch in the loader, the node performs forward and backward passes to minimize the cross-entropy loss:

$$L = - \sum_{k=1}^{10} y_k \log p_k$$

where y_k is the one-hot encoded true label and p_k is the predicted probability for class k . Gradients are computed via backpropagation, and model weights θ are updated as:

$$\theta \leftarrow \theta - \eta \cdot \nabla_{\theta} L$$

Weight Upload:

After completing one full local epoch, the worker saves its trained model parameters (`state_dict`) to a file named: `weights.pt_<worker-ip>`

It then uploads this file to the master node by sending a POST request to: `/receiveweights`

The system includes a robust retry mechanism, attempting the upload up to 5 times with increasing delays (exponential back-off) to ensure reliability under unstable network conditions.

F. Phase 4 - Weight Synchronization, Aggregation, and Model Update

Once each worker node completes a local training epoch, it must synchronize with the master node to contribute its learned parameters to the global model. This process consists of three tightly connected sub-phases: **weight upload and tracking, aggregation, and distribution of the updated model**

Weight Upload and Synchronization :

Each worker saves its trained model parameters as a PyTorch *state_dict* in a file named: `weights.pt_<worker_ip>`

It then uploads this file to the master using:

POST/receiveweights

To ensure robustness, the system includes up to 5 retries with exponentially increasing wait times. The master node uses a Synchronizer object to track the uploads. For each worker:

It stores the uploaded weight file as:

`worker_<ip>_epoch_<e>.pt`

It sets a flag:

`received_weights[ip]←True`

Aggregation is triggered only when:

$\forall ip \in \text{WORKER_NODES}, \text{received_weights}[ip]=\text{True}$

Compute-Aware Model Aggregation :

Upon receiving all worker weights for a given epoch *ee*, the master aggregates them using a softmax-based weighted average, influenced by each node's compute capacity (inferred from the **gmark2** benchmark scores).

Let θ_i denote the model parameters from worker *ii*, and rank_i be the benchmark score for that node.

First, the master computes a softmax distribution over all valid ranks:

$$W_i = \frac{e^{\frac{\text{rank}_i}{\tau}}}{\sum_{j=1}^K e^{\frac{\text{rank}_j}{\tau}}} \quad (1)$$

where τ is a temperature constant (set to 3 in this system).

The global model θ_{global} is then computed using weighted averaging over all received models:

$$\theta_{\text{global}} = \sum_{i=1}^K W_i \theta_i \quad (2)$$

This approach ensures that faster or more reliable nodes contribute more to the global update, improving training efficiency and reducing the impact of weak participants.

Distribution of Global Weights and Worker Update :

After the master node completes aggregation of all worker weights, it initiates the distribution and update phase to ensure all nodes are synchronized for the next round of training.

First, the master saves the newly aggregated global model

weights into a canonical file named `weights.pt`.

This file represents the unified model parameters after incorporating contributions from all workers during the current epoch.

Next, the **master sends these updated weights** to each worker node by making a POST request to their `/receiveweights` endpoint. This step ensures every worker receives the exact same version of the global model.

To coordinate the next steps, the master **notifies all worker nodes that aggregation is complete** by sending a POST request to each worker's `/aggregation_complete` endpoint. This informs the workers that it is safe to proceed with loading the new model and starting the next epoch.

Upon receiving the notification, each **worker downloads the updated global weights** from the master via a GET request to the `/weights` route. Once the file is received, the worker **loads the weights into its local model** using:

`model.load_state_dict(weights.pt)`

With the updated model in place, the worker proceeds to the next local training epoch. If the current epoch is the final round (i.e., $e=E-1$), the worker concludes its training and exits gracefully.

This carefully synchronized cycle guarantees that **every node is working on the same global model at each epoch**, ensuring consistency and convergence of the distributed learning process, even across devices with differing compute capabilities.

G. Process-Completion Logic and Final Output

The training protocol terminates deterministically when the global epoch counter reaches the user-defined value **EPOCHS** (default = 10). The exact sequence at the last round is:

Final aggregation After the master has received every worker's weights for epoch $E-1$, it executes Algorithm 3 one last time.

Global broadcast The aggregated parameters are pushed to all workers via *POST/receiveweights*, followed by the `/aggregation_complete` notification with payload

`{"epoch": E-1, "master_ip": MASTER_IP}`.

Workers acknowledge & exit Upon receipt, each worker: downloads the final global weights (`GET/weights`); loads them into memory (`load_state_dict`); breaks out of its training loop because the outer for epoch in `range(EPOCHS)`: has finished; prints a completion banner and returns control to the operating system.

Master log & model persistence

Prints "[IP][Master] All aggregation rounds complete."

Saves the canonical file `weights.pt` in the project root, which now contains the converged global model θ_{final} .

Optionally invokes `Trainer.test_model()` to compute accuracy on the MNIST test set and export two artefacts:

Console report – overall accuracy in %

Image file – mnist_predictions.png, a 2 × 5 montage of test samples with predicted vs. true labels .

Documentation snapshot generate_md_documentation() (called once at start-up) leaves an Obsidian-formatted markdown file summarising:

the elected master, the worker list and their ranks, hyper-parameters (batch size, learning rate, epochs), and a timestamped record of each aggregation round.

Flask lifetime The Flask server processes remain alive after training finishes, allowing:

later retrieval of weights.pt via GET /weights; ad-hoc inference requests if extended with a /predict route.

Termination criterion.

Process

complete (epoch_num=EPOCHS-1)^(all_weights_received=True)

Under this condition every node holds an identical copy of θ_{final} ; no further messages are exchanged except voluntary inference calls or manual shutdown commands.

V. RESULTS AND OUTCOME

This project partially demonstrates a lightweight, LAN-based distributed learning framework that allows multiple heterogeneous devices—such as laptops or edge systems connected to the same Wi-Fi network—to collaboratively train a machine learning model without centralizing their data. The system dynamically discovers available nodes in the local network through a ping sweep and evaluates their computational performance using a graphics benchmark (glmark2). Based on the benchmark scores, the node with the lowest performance is elected as the master, while the others become workers.

In the observed experimental setup, devices were correctly identified and assigned their roles based on their benchmark scores. For example, one device scored 4470 and was classified as a worker. Although some devices were unreachable due to connection failures, the system handled these by retrying requests and marking failed connections with default error scores. This behavior shows the robustness of the role-assignment logic even in partially available network environments.

1. Sample predictions from the final model evaluated on the MIT variant of the MNIST dataset. Each subplot displays a test image with its ground truth (True) and the model's predicted label (Pred).

2. Sample predictions from the final model evaluated on the MIT variant of the MNIST dataset. Each subplot displays a test image with its ground truth (True) and the model's predicted label (Pred).

Each worker device trained a shared neural network model (an MLP for MNIST classification) on its own local subset of the dataset. After completing each training round (or local epoch), workers attempted to send their model weights to the master node via HTTP. Despite some transmission failures due to unreachable masters, the retry mechanism with exponential backoff ensured resilience in the weight uploading process.

Once all workers' weights were received, the master node aggregated them and redistributed the resulting global model back to all participants. This cycle repeated for a defined number of global epochs, defaulting to ten. The protocol attempted to include synchronization mechanisms to ensure that no node moved ahead before others had completed their part in the current round.

Upon reaching the final epoch, the master performed a final aggregation and saved the converged global model to disk. It then evaluated the model on the standard MNIST test dataset, achieving a final accuracy of 92%. This result validates the effectiveness of the approach in training a strong model despite splitting the data across devices. The system also generated a visual output image (mnist_predictions.png) that displayed sample test predictions, providing a visual confirmation of the model's classification performance.

Additionally, the entire process was logged in a markdown-based documentation file, recording the participating nodes, their roles, benchmark scores, and training hyperparameters.

In conclusion, the system reliably demonstrated distributed learning across multiple devices with varying compute capabilities on a shared local network. It successfully distributed both the computation and the data, maintained consistency across nodes, and delivered an accurate model without requiring data centralization—making it a strong foundation for decentralized machine learning in edge computing environments.

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